

Library Tour: Circular Economy Exhibition - plastics, batteries, biowaste and sustainable life

Aim of the event: Raise awareness of reuse and recycling of plastics, batteries and biowaste. Increase the target group's awareness of a sustainable lifestyle and help them think about their consumption choices.

Target group: Citizens, especially families, children, parents and grandparents. Libraries, decision makers in municipalities.

Description of the event

The circular economy exhibition is organized in the libraries of the five municipalities of Pirkanmaa region during the years 2023-2024. The exhibition tour contains a versatile information package on the circular economy and gives visitors the opportunity to test their circular economy knowledge with the task cards designed for this purpose.

Shared usage is an essential part of circular economy, and this makes libraries good partners for the circular economy exhibition. Many libraries have expanded their offering, in addition to books and music, to include for example hobby equipment. The purpose of the exhibition tour, in addition to sharing circular economy information, is also to increase library visitors' knowledge of everything that can be borrowed from libraries.

The focus of the TREASoURcE circular economy exhibition is on the project's three value chains: batteries, plastics and bio-based side streams. The exhibition also introduces the main principles of sustainable consumption. These are presented in the exhibition with the help of four information boards, on which a compact information package on the topics has been collected. Visitors can also participate and test their skills with the help of task cards specially designed for the exhibition. Another participative task is a recycling game produced by Pirkanmaan Jätehuolto Oy.

In connection with the exhibition, a related seminar is also organized in every municipality. The seminars are planned according to the wishes of the target municipality and are related to the three value chains of the TREASoURcE project.

Tour schedule

Pälkäne 1.9.-29.9.2023,
seminar on the circular economy of plastics for elementary school 7th graders 29.5.2023

Tampere (SWAP! event) 13.10.-14.10.2023

Mänttä-Vilppula 1.11.- 30.11.2023,
seminar on agricultural bio-based side streams and biogas 24.10.2023

Lempäälä 4.1.-15.2.2024

Hämeenkyrö 28.3.-29.4.2024

Tampere (Metso Goes Green-event) 29.4.-6.5.2024

Effectiveness

Pälkäne: 49 people wrote their names in the guestbook of the event, 19 people took part in a survey organized by the library in connection with the exhibition. In the seminar there were 29 7th graders and their five adult tutors.

Tampere: The once-a-year SWAP! clothing exchange event gathered 3 000 participants in the Tampere-talo. The circular economy exhibition was located along the visitors' route, so it achieved a lot of visibility. However, only five visitors stopped to do the exhibition tasks.

Mänttä-Vilppula: In Mänttä library, the exhibition was located in an excellent place, in the middle of the library. During the exhibition, approximately 2 200 people visited the site. There was great interest in the exhibition, the library staff were asked many questions related to the subject. In the seminar there were 28 participants, mostly farmers and municipal government employees.

Lempäälä: In Lempäälä library exhibition was located on the second floor in very visible place. It could be recognized also from the first floor. The library estimated there were x people visiting the exhibition.

Hämeenkyrö: Coming in 2024

In total: 2 335 (+ 3 000 in SWAP!) by the end of November 2023

Media

30.8.2023

Sydän-Hämeen Lehti

A local newspaper in Pälkäne and Kangasala

[Ekokumppanit aloittaa kirjastokierroksensa Pälkäneeltä – kirjasto haluaa lisätä lainattavien retkeilyvälineiden määrää - Sydän-Hämeen Lehti \(shl.fi\)](#)

6.11.2023

KMV-lehti

A local newspaper in Mänttä-Vilppula

<https://www.kmvlehti.fi/elamanmeno/art-2000009965189.html>

7.11.2023

Local business services website

<https://www.manttavilppula.fi/elinkeinoelama/elinkeinoelaman-utisia/ekokumppaneiden-jarjestama-kiertotalousnayttely-mantan-kirjastossa-marraskuun-ajan/>

Feedback

People could give feedback via phones. QR codes were visible on the walls during the exhibitions.

Grade from 1-5	Palaute	Feedback translated into English

Preparations to be taken

1. Find the libraries that are interested in the exhibition and who have a room for it
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2. Agree the topics for the seminar
3. Book transportation for exhibition material
4. Communication
 - Press release
 - Social media campaign
5. Make a list of things needed and collect them. For example:
6. Make a feedback survey for visitors
7. After the event:
 - Transport the exhibition material to storage
 - Analyse feedback surveys and improvement possibilities
 - Final report

